
Determining pasture evapotranspiration using active optical sensor derived normalized difference vegetation index

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Abstract

Actual evapotranspiration (ET_c) is one of the important parameters that determines the daily and seasonal water requirement by the crop community. It varies with numerous factors including weather, soil moisture availability and other crop related factors such as growing stage, fraction of field coverage and crop vigour. In this study we investigated the relationship between normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) that is closely related to photosynthetically-active biomass (PAB) and the evapotranspiration of pasture at different soil moisture condition. A portable enclosed chamber was used to measure ET_c of a target pasture canopy and consequently the NDVI with a hand held active optical sensor. The portable chamber was calibrated in the laboratory and produced a calibration factor of C=1.02. Field experiments were conducted on the UNE SMART Farm in Tall Fescue pastures (*Festuca arundinacea* var. Dovey). Under limiting soil moisture condition the relationship between NDVI and ET_c showed a negative correlation (R²=0.73) whereas a strong and positive correlation (R²=0.82) were observed in a non-limiting soil moisture condition.

Background

Evapotranspiration (ET) refers to the combination of evaporation from soil and transpiration from plant leaves. Under a set of well known 'standard conditions', the evapotranspiration of a given plant community is known as the ET_a whereas the actual amount of water vapour evapo-transpired from a plant community is denoted as ET_c (Allen et al., 1998). The ratio of ET_c to ET_a is the so-called 'crop coefficient'. Reflectance indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and the rate of evapotranspiration from a crop or pasture canopy (ET_c) are both important indicators of 'vigour', namely the photosynthetic activity and rate of biomass accumulation. Measuring both of these parameters simultaneously, with a view to understanding how they interact, or for creating an optical, surrogate indicator of ET is very difficult because ET itself is difficult to measure. Actual plant evapotranspiration (ET_c) varies seasonally and regionally depending on weather parameters, crop characteristics and management practices (Hanson, 1991; Allen et al., 1998). Current techniques of measuring actual evapotranspiration of a crop in-situ involves indirect methods such as energy balance and microclimatological models, soil water balance or directly using lysimeters. However, these methods are very expensive, difficult to maintain accuracy, time consuming and can only be exploited by experienced and well-trained research personnel. As a consequence their uses are generally constrained to a research context only (Allen et al., 1998).

Remote sensing based agrometeorological models are the least imposing methods of inferring crop evapotranspiration, although, these methods are better suited for the regional scale (Allen et al., 2007). In estimating regional scale ET, remote sensing based algorithms have exhibited accuracies from 67 to 97% and more than 94% for daily and seasonal ET respectively (Gowda et al., 2008).

The success of efficient management of water resources relies upon accurate and reliable estimates of evapotranspiration and optical measures, such as the widely used NDVI potentially offer a convenient means of estimating ET_c . Numerous studies have been reported in estimating evapotranspiration parameters for irrigation water management at regional scale using satellite derived optical reflectance data (Gowda et al., 2008).

The crop coefficient (K_c) is an important parameter of a specific crop community because once known, it can be used to infer the actual crop evapotranspiration from available weather data; the latter which can be used to estimate ET_o . In numerous studies K_c has been related to the derived value of NDVI (Bausch & Neale, 1987; Neale et al., 1990; Neale et al., 2003; Hunsaker et al., 2005; Duchemin et al., 2006; Er-Raki et al., 2007; Allen et al., 2010; Johnson & Trout, 2012; El-Shirbeny et al., 2014; Nouri et al., 2014) calculated from the spectral reflectance measurements from satellite, airborne or ground based sensors. Recent studies have reported a linear relationship between K_c and NDVI (Hunsaker et al., 2003; Duchemin et al., 2006; Allen et al., 2010). In particular when K_c is broken up into its soil only evaporation component (K_e) and the plant-specific, 'basal' transpiration component (K_{cb}) the linearity between NDVI and K_{cb} is evident (Neale et al., 2005). The K_{cb} -NDVI relationship has shown a great potential in irrigation water management at the regional scale when soil evaporation is negligible. Moreover, the similarity between the seasonal patterns of NDVI and K_{cb} indicates the potential robustness of linking NDVI with K_{cb} (Er-Raki et al., 2007; Rafn et al., 2008; Nouri et al., 2014).

Handheld, active optical sensors such as GreenSeeker® (Trimble, Sunnyvale, California, USA) or the CropCircle® (Holland Scientific Inc., Lincoln, NE, USA) can measure the NDVI of the target plant canopy instantly regardless of the environmental conditions using the principle of active optical sensing (AoS) (Holland et al., 2012). Since ET and NDVI are closely related to each other, to see the correlation between them it is desired that the crop evapotranspiration can be measured at the same spatial scale, and as near as coincident (in time) and from the very same target canopy. One solution is the use of a hemispherical evaporation chamber for directly recording evapotranspiration in situ (Stannard, 1988). This is a convenient method requiring a few minutes onsite to set up the instruments and less than a minute to take a measurement (McLeod et al., 2004). A number of studies have been conducted to measure the local evapotranspiration in a range of environmental conditions in forests and even a desert environment (McJannet et al., 1996; Garcia et al., 2008; Macfarlane & Ogden, 2012), vegetated rangelands (Stannard & Wertz, 2006), in pasture and in other crops (Stannard, 1988; McLeod et al., 2004) using closed hemispherical chambers. Calibration of the chamber before field measurement and mixing of air and vapour inside the chamber during measurement are both crucial steps as they can influence the measurement accuracy substantially. The calibration factor C, which describes the accuracy at which the evaporation dome measurements can account for the actual water losts from the plant-soil system to the air (where it is measured) varies from 1.08 (Macfarlane & Ogden, 2012) up to 1.53 (McLeod et al., 2004) in previous studies demonstrating the uncertainties of this technique. Therefore, careful calibration and careful operation in the field is important for successful use of this method. Nevertheless, comparing the performance of this chamber approach with other theoretical approaches of measuring ET (McLeod et al., 2004) have demonstrated the potential of this method for evaluating an indirect measurement of evapotranspiration.

With the ever-growing interest in remote sensing for irrigation management, the availability of high spatial resolution multispectral satellite systems and the emergence of ultra-high spatial resolution aerial platforms such as drones, and small handheld AoS reflectance devices, there is considerable interest in being able to conveniently derive K_c from optical measures. A key aim of this study is to

develop and test a sampling protocol involving the portable dome approach and handheld AoS, and involving the near-coincident measurements of ET_c and the optical reflectance index (e.g. NDVI) to understand the relationship between optical and evaporation characteristics of the canopies in question. This paper reports on the initial phase of work concerning the relationship between NDVI and ET_c in two different scenarios of soil moisture availability.

Methods

A portable perspex dome, based on the design of McLeod (2004) was developed to quickly and conveniently determine ET_c of emerging pasture and crop canopies in an area of 0.36 m^2 . The rapidly accumulating water vapour over the enclosed canopy is circulated to overhead sensors where the temperature and relative humidity are used to determine the instantaneous ET_c using the ideal gas and molar mass equations.

Prior to field deployment, the instruments were prepared and calibrated in the laboratory of Physics and Electronics Department, University of New England, Australia and the field data subsequently collected from the experimental plot located on the SMART Farm of the University of New England, Armidale, NSW, Australia. The study was conducted during the summer in 2016 and 2017. The pasture species in the experimental plot was Tall Fescue (*Festuca arundinacea* var. Dovey). The schematic diagram of the instrument setup in field measurement is shown in Figure 1.

The basic methodology for instrumentation and calibration followed the previous studies of McLeod et al. (2004) and Stannard (1988). The diameter of the dome is 0.68 m and the height is 0.36 m including the foam on its base. A humidity sensor (Vaisala Oy, HMP 35A, Helsinki) and a thermocouple (ICT International, Australia) were mounted inside the dome to monitor the change in internal environment and the sensors were connected with a data logger (SM1E904, ICT International, Australia) which was able to record the data at one second intervals. Two fans of 80 cm diameter were inserted into the dome to mix the air and water vapour uniformly. The sensors receive power from the data logger which was directly connected to a laptop and a portable rechargeable battery was used to run the fans.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the dome fitted with necessary accessories.

For the purpose of calibrating the instrument in laboratory, the basic principle of producing vapour inside the dome at a known rate and comparing it with that inferred from the overhead sensors followed that of McLeod et al. (2004) and Stannard (1988). The rate of vapour produced inside the chamber from a test water body was varied and the instantaneous amount of water lost into the contained atmosphere within the dome calculated with the help of a balance (PA413C, Ohaus, USA,

Precision balance) having an accuracy of 0.001 g. The rate of vapour production compared to the rate of vapour accumulation in the dome was used to determine the calibration factor (C).

Field data were collected during the summer of 2016 and 2017 under two different soil moisture conditions. The pastures were in full growth phase and the photosynthetic vigour was varied by applying different doses of fertilizer. For the first experiment the field was allowed to dry for a week period with no rainfall occurred or irrigation applied. In another experiment the same field was irrigated sufficiently before taking the data to ensure that the soil moisture was not limiting the evapotranspiration. During each experiment the data was collected in a 30 minute window close to noon under clear sky conditions.

For each dome measurement, the target plant sample was covered by the dome for approximately 60 to 90 seconds and the temperature and relative humidity used to calculate the progressive accumulation of vapour.

From the accumulated mass of water plotted against time curves, the slope (M) of the linear portion of the plotted curve (g/s) that occurs immediately after the atmosphere inside the dome stabilises after dome placement over the plants, was used to calculate the instantaneous crop evapotranspiration. The crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) in mm/hr was calculated using the equation (Stannard, 1988).

$$\text{Crop Evapotranspiration (ET}_c\text{)} = 3.6 \frac{MC}{A} \text{ mm/hr} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, M is the slope of the straight line portion (g/s), C is the calibration factor (in this case observed to be 1.02), A is the area of the target crop covered by the dome (m²) and 3.6 is the unit conversion factor.

On completion of each dome measurement, the average NDVI of the same target sample were recorded using a GreenSeeker (Trimble, Handheld crop sensor) following the manufacturer's recommended protocol.

Results

The initial laboratory testing elicited device settings and analytical process appropriate to extracting the ET_c values. Firstly, using the 'calibrating evaporating water body', it was verified that the sensors can account for the vapour produced inside the dome accurately in less than 20 seconds (Figure 2). The system produced a calibration Factor, C = 1.02 with R² = 0.87 which is comparable to other workers using similar systems (Macfarlane & Ogden, 2012).

Figure 2. Vapour removal (balance reading) data plotted against accumulation (sensor reading) data to produce the calibration factor (C = 1.02) which is the slope of the fitted line passing through the origin.

Figure 3. Field measurement of ET_c values were plotted against corresponding NDVI values (Full growth and limited soil moisture condition)

The results of measuring ET_c and NDVI for the water limited and non-water limited pasture sites are given in Figure 3 and 4. In a limited soil moisture condition the actual evapotranspiration was found to be very low (0.05 to 0.12 mm/h) which produced a negative correlation with NDVI with an $R^2 = 0.73$ (Figure 3). This is because the exposed soil was likely dominating as a source of water loss (i.e. through evaporation) and the plants were likely dormant in the midday sun. With increasing NDVI (cover) the soil evaporation is reduced. The plant is contributing negligible vapour into the dome via transpiration. The NDVI- ET_c relationship was observed to change dramatically when the site was revisited under non limiting soil moisture conditions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Field measurement of ET_c values were plotted against corresponding NDVI values (Full growth and non-limiting soil moisture condition)

A strong positive correlation was found between ET_c and the corresponding NDVI values ($R^2=0.82$) for the moist conditions (Figure 4). The estimated actual crop evapotranspiration varies from 0.29 to 0.92 mm/h in that condition.

Of importance in this pair of experiments, is that the relationship between evapotranspiration and NDVI alters with the soil moisture availability. In this work, where the water conditions were only short term, the change of the ET_c -NDVI relationship is dominated by the changing ET_c values in response to the conditions rather than the NDVI values.

Conclusion

NDVI as a single parameter is unable to be used to estimate the water demand of the pasture in a water stress condition but the strong positive correlation between NDVI and evapotranspiration in a non-limiting soil moisture condition shows a good prospect that it can be used to estimate ET_c or crop water requirement. An extensive array of field measurements is now required to confirm the relationship between the canopy optical reflectance properties and ET_c under a range of soil and canopy conditions.

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